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STEM UNIVERSITIES AND THEIR RESPONSE TO THE COVID-IMPOSED DIGITAL MOVE: A COMPREHENSIVE OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

In the last decades, Higher Education has undergone an ever-increasing trend of digitalisation. Universities have already been working for years on adapting to the digital era, with new technologies and increased accessibility driving educators towards adopting new teaching methods. In this context, the sudden outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic enforced changes that would have taken years to happen in just a few months. Now that digital education is no longer optional, universities have been urged to adapt to an online environment, using a wide variety of approaches. This research aims at centralizing all the scattered knowledge that has been generated in the emergency-focused response to the pandemic, to turn it into a collection of best practices for educators and STEM universities. This study was run on a pool of 50 universities from 28 countries, by conducting interviews with students from each institute between November 2020 and February 2021, analyzed through content analysis and thematic analysis techniques. These interviews covered 5 main areas: Teaching methods adapted to the online environment; Digital tools used for online lectures; Online laboratories; Online assessment methods; Personal interaction between students or students and educators in an online environment. The paper finally recommends techniques that educators can use to create a more effective and digital-enhanced learning experience for their students, with the right balance of digital content and in-person interaction. It also advises actions that universities can take to support educators in achieving this goal, and to digitally enhance interaction between their students and educators.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The latest advances in the field of technology, such as continuous connectivity, increased digitisation, and instant access to information, led to redefining many aspects of both professional and daily life. In this context, digital education has evolved and has become a vital part of this digital revolution, making use of the most modern technologies to create an optimal learning environment focused on students.

In the latest months following the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, the digitisation process has been exponentially accelerated. Universities had to adopt technology and digital tools as part of their standard methodology in no time [1]. Even though the COVID-19 crisis has caused many challenges, new insights and ideas on the topic have arisen which can lay the groundwork to drive the change in education for the next years.

Specifically, higher education had already been in the digitalisation process for a decade[2], but universities adapted at different speed and in different ways to the new needs the pandemic imposed. The knowledge generated on this adaptation process has not yet been organised and shared among institutions rigorously and systematically. Findings are scattered and uniquely used in specific universities, or even just in particular courses. Therefore, centralising and evaluating the information acquired over the last year can provide the tools to create the basis for digitally-enhanced education in a post-pandemic context[3].

With these ideas in mind, this research aims at centralising the scattered knowledge that has been generated in the emergency-focused response to the pandemic and to turn it into a collection of teaching best practices for educators and STEM universities. The paper provides a comprehensive overview, based on the students' perspective, of the actions taken by universities in the fields of (online) teaching methods, digital tools, (online) assessment methods, and university support for (online) interaction. It aims at helping to design new approaches to digital education, by providing concrete examples of other European universities.

Consequently, this research approaches the following questions: How did European STEM Universities tackle the transition from in-person to digital education? How were teaching and assessment methods adapted? Which tools were used to support them? What are the best actions to be taken?

2 METHODOLOGY

The data presented in this paper was gathered through a series of interviews with one student from each university in the sample. We interviewed students in pairs, with 4 different interviewers. We conducted interviews in 50 STEM universities from 28 European countries, in the period between November 2020 and February 2021. Using a pre-designed script, each interviewer was going through a series questions, recording the interview in form of raw texts and checkboxes.

The interview had the goal of gathering factual information about the measures that each university took in facing the pandemic. To extend the information gathered in the interview to the whole university, rather than just the specific experience of each interviewee, we contacted interviewees 1-2 weeks before the interview itself. We provided 5 questions on the topics that the interview would touch upon, asking the interviewee to gather more information about it from his/her peers, to then report to us. This, together with the fact that we were probing for factual information (and not opinions, for which statistics is of essence), was done to mitigate the concern that a sample of one student per university wouldn't be representative.

We designed the interview script¹ to cover 5 areas: the general approach of the university regarding teaching activities, tools used for online teaching, online teaching methods, online assessment methods, and university support for students.

¹<https://bit.ly/33c8MC2>

We conducted the first 3 interviews with a slightly different script, used for testing and fine-tuning. For this reason, those have not been included in the statistics in the paper, which will only be about the remaining 47 universities. Nevertheless, the ideas gathered in those 3 initial interviews are reported in the text throughout the paper.

After this, we analysed the data analysis by using thematic analysis[4] and content analysis[5] techniques, to bring responses from raw text to a format that allowed statistical analysis.

The analysis process consisted of an iterative process between 3 steps.

1. **Assigning codes to meaning units in the text:** We went through the text of all interviews and assigned a code to any found meaning unit. In this context, a meaning unit refers to each piece of information that has been collected from the students.
2. **Reviewing the code list:** While creating codes, we logged them in a codebook, with the name and description of the meaning unit the code was capturing. This allowed reviewing the codes within the team, and it minimised cognitive bias throughout the codifying process.
3. **Grouping those codes in themes:** After creating and reviewing the codes, we looked for themes[4] within them. In this context, a theme refers to a specific pattern found in the data. Each theme captures some crucial information about the data in relation to the research questions, and features patterned meanings across the data set. Codes were rearranged, merged, and deleted, to find meaningful trends and patterns.

The last step was to format the created codes as boolean values tables, to be able to run statistical analysis effectively.

3 RESULTS

3.1 General situation in the university

This section investigates how universities adapted their traditionally organised activities to the online format. For more clarity, we define below the four main activities, as their meaning may differ depending on the university or on the major:

- **Courses:** theoretical lectures;
- **Practical lectures:** all the activities where students apply their knowledge or do practical experiments;
- **Assessments:** projects, midterms, and final exams;
- **Research activities:** research conducted by any student, as a part of a research team in the university or for his/her diploma project.

3.1.1 Observations

Universities took a wide variety of long-term and short-term measures to quickly adapt to the outbreak of the pandemic. While some universities adapted quickly to online learning, using the already existing infrastructure, others were taken by surprise: 7 out of 47 universities (10%) had cancelled classes in order to prepare a plan and update their infrastructure to support digital education.

Figure 1a geographically shows the approaches that universities took in the adaptation, either fully moving online or using hybrid approaches with some activities still live. scenarios adopted by the universities. 39 out of 47 universities (83%) used a hybrid approach, trying to conduct offline activities when possible, while 8 universities had online classes exclusively, starting from March 2020.

Following the trends present in all aspects of society, universities tried to reduce the number of participants in live activities, in order to limit the number of interactions between people. 38% of the universities from this study have tried different approaches that would permit safe offline

activities, such as:

- Dividing students into two groups that were alternating in class;
- Organising an on-campus day a week, to group all live activities together;
- Having all classes at reduced capacity and introducing a booking system for students.

To further elaborate on the type of activities that still happened live, Figure 1b presents a histogram of the activities that universities tried to organise offline. We can observe that 23% tried to organise offline courses, and 21% encouraged research activities to happen live. Additionally, 55% of the universities have tried to have practical lectures fully or partially offline, while 49% universities tried to have in-person assessments, rather than online ones, with a total percentage of 30% universities trying to provide offline solutions for both practical lectures and assessments.

Figure 1: (a) Geographical distribution of the universities trying hybrid approaches. (b) Histogram representing which activities universities tried to organize offline. The codes in the histogram are non-exclusive, so the total counts add up to more than the total of 47 universities in the analysed database

3.1.2 Discussion and Conclusion

Although all the activities mentioned in this section have an online equivalent, 40 out of 47 universities (85%) have tried to organise at least one type of the above-mentioned activities in an offline manner. Based on this, we notice that universities have made considerable efforts to organise as many activities as possible live and to maintain the safety conditions, that could flag that these are considered important to ensure good learning experiences for the students.

Additionally, based on Figure 1b, it is noticeable that most universities focused on having practical lectures and assessment sessions live, rather than remote. Considering that STEM disciplines partially rely on practical, hands-on experience and can require special equipment only present in a designated laboratory, the need for having offline practical lectures is logical, and it is reflected in the data of this section.

3.2 Digital tools

In this section, we give an overview of the tools that have been used in European STEM universities for different activities. We also analyse which resources the universities provided to students and professors, and present the approach that different universities had on practical lectures.

3.2.1 Observations

We probed the interviewed students upon which tools have been used for both theoretical & practical lectures, and for sharing study material. There was no significant difference observed between tools used for theoretical lectures and practical lecture, just using more interactive features like breakout rooms for the second ones.

We can see in Figure 2a that most of the universities used non-integrated video-conferencing tools. Zoom and Microsoft Teams were by far the most used, with 34 (72%) and 28 (60%) cases, but also Google Meet, Skype, and Webex were mentioned. There was also a significant number of universities that used video-conferencing tools fully integrated with their university platform, the most common being Moodle-based platform (32%), including its plugins like BigBlueButton (7 cases, 15%, included in “Moodle-based” in the figure). But we can also see other tools like Google Classroom and Blackboard Collaborate, or unspecific University websites hosting streaming/recordings.

Additionally, other tools were used in parallel to increase online interaction. The main ones reported were Kahoot (8 times, 17%) and Google form (4 times) for quizzes, and even Miro for having a more collaborative environment for the class (2 times).

Figure 2b shows the same analysis on the tools used for sharing study material. A tool integrated into the university platform was used more often than in Figure 2a, with Moodle being the most widespread (51%), and a university website (non-Moodle-based) also being very common (43%). Also here, we notice non-integrated methods for sharing materials like emails (13%), Microsoft Teams (11%), and others. Blackboard Collaborate was only reported once, Google Drive and Google Classroom twice, they are included in the “Other tools” column.

Figure 2: (a) Histogram of the tools used for lectures. (b) Histogram of the tools used for sharing material (slides, assignments,...) between professors and students. The codes in the plots are non-exclusive, so the total counts add up to more than the total of 47 universities in the analysed database

We also analysed the university support in providing tools to educators. In almost all cases, the university did provide educators with some sort of tool. In 15 cases (32%), tools were centrally provided. In 15 other cases, there were tools provided by the university, but some of the professors were not using them and were resorting to custom (eventually free) ones. In 12 cases (26%), the tools were provided and used, but some educators also used additional non-university-provided ones in parallel (e.g. Miro or Kahoot together with Zoom). In 3 cases the interviewee mentioned that tools were provided only in the second semester, and in 2 cases that the educators did not have any provided tool.

3.2.2 Discussion and Conclusion

The move to digital education needs to be empowered by a series of tools that support universities, professors, and students in interacting in an online environment. In the context of the rise of the COVID-19 pandemic, professors and students have worked in integrating these tools into Higher Education, possibly with the support of university bodies.

All universities have used at least one video-conferencing tool that was allowing for live interaction between students and educators, and one tool for sharing material between students and educators. We considered these to be the essential elements needed to be able to run an online class.

We presented in this section a large variety of used digital tools, with professors that tested many of those independently. This was probably an inefficient time-drain, as many different educators had to go through the same process in parallel. It also highly relies on the single

educator, which is a weak strategy due to the vastly differing skill sets of different educators. We therefore advise universities to support educators by providing them with an adequate framework of digital tools that they can use for their classes, after an eventual round of needs gathering. This will allow them to focus on what they are experts at: the content of their lectures.

The approaches visible in this part are included in a spectrum within:

- A fully-decentralised approach, where educators were independently figuring out the best tools to use, and aligning with the students. An example would be having lectures via a Skype call set up by the educator, who also shares the links and materials via email to all the students.
- A fully-centralised approach, where the university provides a central tool with the course schedule, links to the video-lectures, space to upload materials and ask questions. To the knowledge of the authors of this paper, Moodle and Blackboard Collaborate support this feature.

In the middle of the spectrum are approaches where there is a university website to share materials, and that the educator can use to share links to lectures and materials, eventually with software licences provided by the university.

A fully-decentralised approach can be more flexible and agile, but it relies more heavily on single educators to handle the logistics of the online class and to work through the myriad of tools available. A fully-centralised approach requires more resources from the university to be effective. The university also needs to set up and maintain the system and gather requirements and give trainings to educators, otherwise there is the risk that they will not make use of the supplied tools, as seen at the end of the previous section (3.2.1). However, this approach supports the educators more, leaving them larger bandwidth to focus on the content of their classes.

3.3 Teaching methods

This section studies how teaching methods were adapted to the online environment, to conduct lecture, maintain engagement, and ask questions. Throughout this paper, we will use the term "teaching method" to refer to "the general principles, pedagogy and management strategies used for classroom instruction"[6]

3.3.1 Observations

To start, we investigated in the interviews the degree of change that occurred in teaching methods. 72% of the students stated that there was no noticeable change in the teaching methods when moving to online education. Adaptations consisted uniquely on the platform used (not a physical class, but an online class), but not on the way information was delivered. The main reports were that educators were using the same presentations as they would use in an offline classroom. On the other hand, there were 17% who affirmed that changes in the techniques were noticeable with respect to on site education.

In Figure 3a, we report the most popular teaching methods. The most common were having lectures recorded (42%), presentations (40%), or Live-streams (15%). 13% also used a Flipped Classrooms². methodology and 11 (23%) used breakout rooms for group activities. Finally, 4 universities also used videos from external resources to explain concepts. Lastly, and 2 introduced a measure to make lessons shorter for maintaining the focus of students.

As a general trend, we observed that measures and techniques depended mostly on the individual teachers rather than on the whole institution, as reported in 62% of the interviews. In addition, 11% of the universities proclaimed that the adaptation to online learning evolved later

²Type of blended learning where students are introduced to content in advance and practice working through it in class

in the pandemic, getting better in the new term in September 2020.

Figure 3: (a) Histogram showing the teaching methods used during the pandemic. (b) Histogram showing the engagement activities used in online classes. The codes in the plots are non-exclusive, so the total counts add up to more than the total of 47 universities in the analysed database.

We also investigated in the interviews which activities were used to maintain students' engagement during the lectures, summarised in Figure 3b. The most common one was organising short quizzes during the lectures (47%). Other often used methods were about asking questions, either from students to educators (34%), or all the way around (19%). Breakout sessions or quick exercises/tests were also used 28% and 30% of the time. A few students mentioned that the professor was probing the class to sharpen attentiveness, either asking questions or checking attendance (15%).

Asking questions is an important step of understanding a piece of information and, while in a traditional offline environment there is no need for a special framework for this, the digital environment made it more difficult to address spontaneous questions. Various solutions used for question answering are presented in Figure 4, both for questions during the lectures, and outside of the lectures.

Figure 4: Overview of the methods offered to students for questions. The codes in the plot are non-exclusive, so the total counts add up to more than the total of 47 universities in the analysed database.

As we can see, most universities used spontaneous methods for questions during lectures: raising hands or unmute in the used video-conference tool (81%) and using the chat to write doubts (72%), where questions were also answered sometimes. Two universities also set up something more elaborate like having a moderator dedicated to collecting and eventually answering questions. On top of that, many universities also provided ways to ask questions outside of lectures. They mostly used emails from students to the educators (53%), and a forum-like environment where both students, educators, and teaching assistants could answer questions (30%). Other options like having office hours that students could book (eventually in groups) or representatives of the class asking for the whole class (for more organizational questions) were used in some universities. In 2 cases, even a mentor professor was assigned to each student.

3.3.2 Discussion and Conclusion

At the beginning of this section we have seen that students do not perceive that changes were made regarding the teaching methods. Most of the teaching methods used were indeed “classical” presentation-like lecturing (both in a video-conference, recorded, or live-stream), even if we can also see more elaborate techniques used for having more discussions within the class (breakout rooms or flipped classroom). On a similar note, for asking questions both during class and outside, most of the approaches were spontaneous ones, much similar to a standard live setting. This could indicate that these approaches work just as well in an online environment as in a live environment.

However, there were also a few methods that made use of the additional opportunities that a digital environment offers. A forum-like environment, much used in online communities for knowledge sharing (Stack Overflow being a famous example), can also enhance the effectiveness of the communication within a course, since all the students can see the answers to questions asked, and they can even answer each other. This also happened in the engagement activities of Figure 3b, where quizzes or breakout rooms do make use of the more digitalised environment.

This all, combined with the fact that the change was usually highly dependent on single educators, could flag that teachers, being under high stress, did not have the time to revise their teaching methods for the new environment. Due to the time pressure, they might have been forced to focus all their energies on keeping everything running while adapting to the new digital infrastructure, with only a limited pool of educators independently finding some space for innovation. However, some of the techniques seen in this section could eventually also be integrated in digitally-enhanced live classes in the future.

We have seen in this section that many educators tried to stick to classical ways of teaching like presenting, trying to fit it directly to an online environment. This could be because of the high stress given by the COVID-19 context, and because they already had to spend time and resources in figuring out the tools to use. However, a few positive approaches that made use of the strength and flexibility of online lectures were tried, with some of those being desirable also in a normal setting. These should be properly propagated and used among educators, integrating them into the classroom of the future. In this time of emergency, much was left to the educators themselves but, in the coming years, universities could facilitate knowledge sharing in this regard by creating platforms for that, such as conferences, courses, or discussions, to make sure that educators have the necessary knowledge to innovate in their lectures

3.4 Assessment Methods

At the rise of the pandemic, universities had the challenge of finding a reliable way to examine students' learning outcome in an online environment. In this section, we report the main techniques and adaptations that were used for this.

3.4.1 Observations

Figure 5a shows that more than 50% of universities had a significant or partial change in assessment methods, 69% of the answers excluding the “Unclear” category. In 11 cases, there was a significant change, with a completely new way of determining the grade (e.g. cancelling the exam and moving the grade to a project). 15 other cases only had a partial change, with the same format but different structure (e.g. changing a closed book exam to an open book exam). In 9 cases it barely changed, meaning that only the necessary things to adapt to an online examination like the platform were changed. Only in 3 cases, the assessment did not change at all.

Figure 5: (a) Pie chart showing the degree of change in assessment methods. The codes in the pie chart are exclusive, so they add up to the total of 47 universities in the analysed database. (b) Geographical visualization of the same data.

Figure 6a reports the format used for online exams. We can see that the exams were mainly carried out in written (66%) and assignment-based (72%) form. Oral exams were done in 17 cases (36%), with some students mentioning that oral exams were removed.

Figure 6: (a) Histogram with an overview of the assessment methods that were used. (b) Histogram with an overview of the used methods to ensure fairness. “Constrained test” means that students were not allowed to go back to previous questions after submitting their answers. “Diversify exam structure” means that the order of questions and/or the parameters for exercises are changed for each student individually. The codes in the plots are non-exclusive, so the total counts add up to more than the total of 47 universities in the analysed database.

Figure 6b presents how universities ensured the fairness of the examination and avoided cheating. There were 2 main categories of methods to ensure fairness: monitoring (e.g. mandatory camera usage, online proctoring tools like a lockdown browser that did not allow using anything else on the PC, recording the exam, or having tests where you cannot go back), reformatting the existing evaluations (e.g. making it shorter, different versions of the exam papers). Making camera usage mandatory was the most popular method to ensure fairness during examination, with 29 cases (62%). All other methods had a similar number of universities that used them. It is worth noting that some of the students reported that Blackboard Collaborate (the tool used for lectures and sharing material) was also used for exams, since it supported a lockdown browser window that only allowed students to use the tab of the exam.

Another approach was restructuring the evaluation to a method where controlling the class was less crucial. Common approaches here were changing to an open book exam or moving to an assignment-based assessment (projects or presentations).

3.4.2 Discussion and Conclusion

It is noticeable that the number of universities which have adapted their evaluation format is a lot larger than the number of universities that changed their educational format (69% vs 17%). This could be because adapting assessment methods were more of a necessity, since the final exam is an integral part of a curriculum, and the professors needed to find solutions to still reliably assess the learning of students.

We can see that the most used method was an assignment-based assessment, with many universities that moved in that direction. This, together with the several different methods adopted in Figure 6b, can indicate that ensuring a fair examination and preventing cheating was one of the pain points, and that an assignment-based assessment by nature works around this.

We have seen in this section the ways the examination was adapted, and several different methods to control and ensure a fair examination, which likely costed a good amount of resources to educators, also seen how common was having a change in assessment methods. For these forced-online circumstances, solutions that worked around this issue by being more assignment-based seem more time-efficient. However, a discussion on whether it would also improve the quality of the course in a post-pandemic would require more thorough evaluations and it is outside of the scope of this paper.

3.5 Training and social support for students

The COVID-19-imposed online move put additional constraints on the digital education framework that universities had to set up, since being remote was suddenly a requirement rather than an option. This forced students and universities to reinvent many of the events that were allowing interaction between students, and it required some new skills for students and educators. This section reports which trainings different universities offered to students and educators, and which actions have been taken to still provide some sort of social interaction among students, which is an essential part of the university experience.

3.5.1 Observations

Another area that the interviews probed upon was the training that educators and students received for online learning and for coping with the online world. For educators, the main ways of training were written guidelines, courses, or video tutorials, that were mentioned about half of the time. However, the students were often unsure about the accuracy of this information.

For students, the results are presented in Figure 7a. The trainings were mainly about using the tools themselves, in the form of video tutorials (32%) or written guidelines (19%). Mental health support was also often mentioned (30%), in the form of seminars or the possibility of having private consultations with psychologists. Often the interviewee reported that these were already there before the pandemic, but they were promoted more after moving online. 8 interviewees (17%) also reported that they had soft skill training on online learning, email communication, coping with stress, and mindfulness. 6 interviewees reported that professors were individually supporting students when needed. Lastly, 11 students (23%) reported that no training was provided.

Figure 7: (a) Histogram showing which training was provided to students. (b) Histogram with an overview of the used methods to ensure fairness. "Constrained test" means that students were not allowed to go back to previous questions after submitting their answers. "Diversify exam structure" means that the order of questions and/or the parameters for exercises are changed for each student individually. The codes in the plots are non-exclusive, so the total counts add up to more than the total of 47 universities analysed.

The last area that this section touched upon was which actions have been taken to provide at least partial social interaction among students. As seen in Figure 7b, NGOs had a big role

in sustaining the social aspect of students' life in these times. Out of the 47 interviewees, 62% mentioned that their social activities were organised by NGOs, 17% mentioned that their social activities were arranged by universities, and 21% mentioned that no social activities were organised at all. 11 of those 29 (38%) mentioned that the NGOs held these without university support, while the other 18 (62%) mentioned that the university supported the NGOs in organising these, either through already-existing collaborations or by commissioning some of the activities. A wide variety of activities has been arranged, most of which included both an academic-related and a social part: Event with companies (presentations, career fairs, or competitions like hackathons); Recruitment events for clubs and NGOs, with social activities; Soft skill trainings; Game nights; Panel discussions among students and professors; Students speed dating

3.5.2 Discussion and Conclusion

We saw in this section that the universities put high efforts in supporting students in adapting to the new digital environment, providing various training and support. Apart from training purely on tool, we also see a care for the emotional situation of students, with measures like providing mental health support, or simply having professors helping out students in their needs.

Another area where students needed support is social interaction that, even if maybe less obvious at first sight, this is a crucial part of the student experience, contributing to the personal growth that those years bring. The lockdown put a strain on this, limiting the possibilities for students to be in contact with their social circle or enlarging it. We can see that most of the universities put effort in (partially) maintaining this part of the students' experience and that NGOs had an important role in helping them achieve this, acting on this area where universities, possibly busy coping with the change, did not have resources or experience to fulfill.

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